

IPAD-MD
Data and Resources Expert Group
Workshop on
iMits and CRISPR information
26-27 June 2017
Schwaig, Germany

MEETING REPORT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 653961

1 Agenda

Monday, 26.06.2017

12:00 – 13:00 Lunch

13:00 – 13:30 Introductions

13:30 – 14:15 iMits overview

14:15 – 15:00 Group discussion - capturing CRISPR information

15:00 – 15:45 Interactions with MGI (Cynthia Smith)

15:45 – 16:15 Coffee

16:15 – 17:00 iMits web services / API

17:00 – 18:30 Tutorial - hands on exercises

19:00 Dinner

Tuesday, 27.06.2017

09:00 – 09:30 iMits generated reports - presentation and discussion

09:30 – 10:00 Gene interest registration

10:00 – 10:30 Other types of data iMits can track

Aging cohorts

Tissue, blocks slides

10:30 – 11:00 Coffee

11:00 – 11:30 Future projects using iMits - Discussion

11:30 – 12:00 Any other business that relates to iMits - Discussion

12:00 – 13:00 Lunch

2 List of participants

Institute	Country	Number of Participants
Baylor College of Medicine	United States of America	2
CNR-IBCN Monterotondo	Italy	3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 653961.

Czech Centre for Phenogenomics, IMG	Czech Republic	3
EMBL-EBI	United Kingdom	2
Helmholtz Zentrum München	Germany	6
INFRAFRONTIER GmbH	Germany	3
Korea Mouse Phenotyping Center (KMPC)	South Korea	2
MRC Harwell	United Kingdom	3
Phenomin-CIPHE	France	1
PHENOMIN-ICS	France	1
RIKEN BioResource Center	Japan	1
The Centre for Phenogenomics	Canada	2
The Jackson Laboratory	United States of America	1
Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute	United Kingdom	2
Baylor College of Medicine	United States of America	2

3 Minutes

3.1 Minute takers

Sabine Fessele (INFRAFRONTIER GmbH) and Peter Matthews/Terry Meehan (EMBL-EBI) were the minute takers. Compiled by Asrar Ali Khan.

3.2 Aims of the workshop

Goals:

- 1) Learn about the new CRISPR based features in iMits and provide feedback
- 2) Help prioritise additional features

The iMits tracking resource of the IMPC is adding a number of additional features to track production of IMPC using CRISPR based methods. To support the user community, IPAD-MD organised the 2017 Data & Resources Expert Group Meeting in Munich on how to use these new methods both via the web interface and the API.

3.3 iMits Overview

Peter Mathews (EMBL-EBI) started off with a detailed description of the workshop outcomes which included understanding the dataflow to the IMPC portal and 'Late Adult' tracking as well as how to register interest in a gene, record CRISPR mouse production and register phenotyping attempts. He also presented detailed workplans for the monitoring of mouse and cohort production and for tracking the flow of phenotyping data. The following new API changes were introduced:

- Simplified the process to characterize CRISPR mouse strain alleles (SCF file now only optional)
- MGI Allele Symbol Suggestor
- Tracking Late Adult Cohorts
- Tracking availability of Fixed Tissues and Section Slides

In addition, EBI would like to get feedback and feature requests from production centres via email impc-imits@ebi.ac.uk. The iMits database structure has also been enhanced. Many new types of information can now be captured in iMits by adding new fields to the GUI.

3.3 Group Discussion - Capturing CRISPR information

The following points were discussed regarding the capturing of CRISPR information:

- Gene symbols in iMits do not always match to what is used in MGI. This can cause duplication of nominations (when generating CRISPR attempt, you are asked to select the gene symbol). Highlighting that a gene symbol has changed since the last log in, might help avoid issues here.
- Often the guide RNA sequences HMGU has used can not be selected, although the IKMC policy on designing guides has been followed. The sequence then needs to be entered by hand, which is tedious. The cause for this restriction is a mechanism that WTSI has put in. Peter will pass this information on to the team responsible for this.
- QC information on IMPC webpage now in EUCOMM format only.
- Information that should be readily available to people entering information in iMits:
 - a) Targeted gene
 - b) Specific targeted genomic location
 - c) gRNA sequence
 - d) Trace files from resulting allele
 - The ABI file from the sequencer needs to be converted to intermediate format like SCF or FASTA. It should also be possible to upload ABI files directly. Especially for conditional mutants, where it is required to upload several (non-contiguous) files.

- The display of the extensive QC information might be too detailed for the end users. Instead they will receive the final GenBank file, (generated by Peter Mathews using the Javascript functionality from WTSI) and can easily sequence the allele if more information is required.
- e) Genotyping primer sequences and PCR conditions should not be stored in iMits but handled at the repository level.
- f) FASTA files
- g) MGI template for allele description
- h) Allele classification with uniform structure/format among INFRAFRONTIER centres.

3.3 Interactions with MGI

An overview of MGI rules for naming allele symbols was presented along with guidelines to produce consistent allele descriptions for IMPC alleles, allele characterization and interactions with MGI.

The following questions were presented from the production centres:

- What is the base pair limit for the sequence that is mentioned?
- Will this be up-to-date if based on position? This needs an update script in place (preferably on the iMits level)
- Will the amino acid sequence be listed as well?

The goal will be to have this calculated and updated automatically from iMits. Peter Matthews started working on this process with Lauryl Nutter and Greg Clark. TCP will collect information and send it to Peter for iMits upload. The TCP tool will later be integrated into iMits

It's important to keep in mind that the clinical community has come up with a nomenclature of human variations, which might lead to further adjustment. However, the clinical system is neither standardized or canonical nor does it have any unique nomenclature system.

Regarding allele naming, the iMits process makes sure 'EM' numbers (Endonuclease Medicated, e.g. EM:11445) are synchronized with MGI. This also includes a feature to suggest EM numbers. Strain IDs are transmitted to MGI from the repositories via the IMSR upload route.

3.4 iMits web services / API

Instead of the planned API discussion, which did not have a lot of discussion points, a few more general issues were brought forward:

- There is a need for clearer definitions for some terms. Examples that were mentioned were 'withdrawn' (given up on gene) vs. 'aborted' (will try again) and 'plan' vs. 'attempt'. It was also suggested to implement a button to conveniently inactivate a plan with all its associated microinjection attempts.
- It was decided to remove the 'priority' field, as this was only needed for ES cell pipelines.

- A quite general feature request brought forward by IMC and UC Davis was to display all rows in any result list with the option to export to SCV/XLS format.

3.5 Tutorial – Hands-on Exercises and User Experience Feedback

The objectives of the hands-on exercise were to:

- Learn to navigate around iMits
- Create microinjection and phenotyping plans
- Create a variety of microinjections for different allele designs
- Learn how to characterize CRISPR alleles
- Share user experiences with the coordinators

The following were the feedback and questions received during the practical exercise:

- A clean list of strain backgrounds (or at least the important ones should be on top) should be present.
- Phenotyping history points to wrong colonies.
- MMRRRC should be designated as the default distribution centre as they do all the distribution.
- 'Cre excision needed' should be removed as the default option for CRISPR as it is not needed.
- Enquiries should now be addressed to impc-imits@ebi.ac.uk for quicker email responses.

3.6 iMits generated reports - presentation and discussion

This session aimed to discuss the process to reset the production counter to zero for (phase 2), assess the current reports (i.e. their usefulness and the needs of the user) and evaluate the need for new reports.

A new notion of a project was introduced. Projects will be assigned to consortia and a consortium can have as many individual projects as required. Plans, colonies and phenotype attempts will be allocated to a project. Moreover, each project will have an overall production goal and each Centre will indicate their planned contribution to each project by setting monthly goals. There was a general agreement that the new concept of 'project' will improve flexibility and also allow for combinations of consortia, centre, data ranges etc.

The following feedback was presented from the audience:

- List of plans with aborted MIs that are still assigned to centres should be offered.
- It is possible to have a list of all genes that are not assigned by downloading and filtering the 'all genes' report.
- CRISPR attempts should be included in 'All planned MI attempts'.
- A monthly activity report would be a welcome addition.
- Downloading data in the form structure would be good. However, this is not that easy because the data not linear any more.
- A list of genes for intended duplication should be sent to Peter Mathews for integration/highlighting in iMits.
- Users are most interested in being informed when germline transmission (GLT) is achieved for a particular gene because this opens up a window of opportunity for further planning. Users might also be informed about Pre-GLT steps.
- RoI (Registration of Interest) users should be informed when projects get dropped.
- Implement a way (eg. Survey) to gauge the interest in specific alleles but at the same time clearly stating that their generation is not guaranteed (manage expectations).

3.7 Gene Interest Registration

With gene interest registration, the IMPC aims to 'keep the scientific community informed about how their genes of interest progress through the IMPC pipeline'.

↑ Screenshot from the IMPC strain search (http://www.mousephenotype.org/data/search/gene?kw=*) showing the 'Register interest' hyperlink.

This is accomplished by having users register interest in genes as shown above. Users are notified via email about the progression of their genes through the IMPC pipeline and also about mouse and phenotyping availability. A new plan to rework email notifications was put forward which included the decision to stop sending ES cell- or CRISPR- centric emails but instead notify the users about the different types of alleles obtained as well as the first and subsequent phenotype data.

The following points were also brought up during the presentation:

- IMPC received 835 RoIs in the first half of 2016 and has planned the production of 526 of them.

- The user enquiry system will be moving away from iMits infrastructure to CDA/IMPC infrastructure (e.g. nomination/RoI from community)
- The centres will use the RoI list to decide which genes to put into their pipeline.
- ES cell-based wording will be replaced with a more allele centric wording.

3.8 Late Adult Phenotyping and Tissue Banking

The latest iMits release can also track the following types of data:

- Aging cohorts
- Progress of the Late Adult Phenotyping
- Tissue and blocks slides availability

It is possible to use the same cohort name for initial and late adult phenotyping. There is a tick box to select late adult phenotyping.

Tissue and block banking can offer several advantages:

1. iMits can provide simple reporting informing centres which of their lines tissues are marked as available.
2. It makes use of the existing iMits Order Management System, providing centres with the options to either receive emails or provide link for ordering.
3. It makes use of the existing data exchange between iMITS and IMPC portal.
4. It does not create further dependencies for IMPC Portal to manage.

The future steps required from member centres and PhenoDCC for the proper functioning of these services included indicating which lines lines/phenotype cohorts will be assigned to late adult phenotyping pipelines, which of these have available tissue sections, ensuring IMPC correctly indicates late adult phenotyping progress etc.

3.9 Future projects using iMits – Discussion

The data model underlining iMits has been adapted to be flexible to allow iMits to quickly adapt to new projects. Using this feature, iMits and IMPC would like to support new mouse production projects that form the basis of future grant proposals or renewals. In order to do this effectively, information about the use of iMits for any new internal projects producing alleles other than the null allele should be provided in advance. The following were potential new projects that could use iMits:

- Different allele types. E.g. Conditional, disease model etc.

- New injection strategies being implemented by centers. E.g. Multiplex injection, donor vector injections etc.
- New QC screens for founders and F1 generations.
- Displaying projects through the IMPC portal.
- Data availability to other sources.

3.10 Decisions and action items INFRAFRONTIER

Unlike previous D&R Expert Group Meetings, there were no general action items for the participants but rather individualized and specific tasks for the service providers which are mentioned in the previous section. As an example, the list of action items for Terry Meehan are given below:

Item	Who	When
Email for feedback and feature requests from production centres	Peter and Terry	July 2017
Remove 'Cre excision needed' as the default option for CRISPR	Terry	August 2017
Designate MMRRRC as the default distribution centre	Terry	August 2017
Implement flexible export tool	Peter	July 2017

3.11 Further documentation

Presentations are available for download at the INFRAFRONTIER internal website.

(<https://www.infrafrontier.eu/internal/ipad-md/expert-group-meetings>)